

Original Research Article

What Counts as Mathematical Proof and Proving? Redesigning a Teacher Education Content Course to Illustrate Liberatory Pedagogies in Action

Saul Pastora

New York University

Syd Stowe

New York University

B Waid¹

California State University—Fullerton

ABSTRACT: This article is focused on the redesigning of a mathematics content course, Mathematical Proof and Proving, offered to pre-service mathematics teachers at a private university in the northeast with a diverse student population. The course redesign was focused on centering anti-racist, queer, and abolitionist pedagogical practices, as well as principles of disability justice in a way that allowed students to experience these pedagogies in action, connecting theory to practice. The article, written by the professor and two pre-service teachers who experienced the course as students, outlines how the professor redesigned the course with these principles in mind and how that redesign was experienced by the two student authors.

KEYWORDS: *queer pedagogy; anti-racist pedagogy; abolitionist teaching; disability justice*

Theory does not solve issues—only action and solidarity can do that—but theory gives you language to fight, knowledge to stand on, and a humbling reality of what intersectional social justice is up against. (Love, 2019, p. 132)

We begin this article with the above quotation by education scholar and abolitionist Dr. Bettina Love because we believe that it captures the essence of this article, where we discuss the use of pedagogical theories to radically reimagine the design and enactment of Mathematical Proof and Proving (MPP), a mathematics content course for pre-service mathematics teachers. The course

¹ Department of Secondary Education, California State University—Fullerton. Correspondence should be addressed to B Waid via email at b.waid@TheQueerMathematicsTeacher.com. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7178-7408>

Received: 13 March 2024 / Revised: 12 October 2024 / Published Online: 20 December 2024

was taught at an ethnically and racially² diverse private university located in New York City and had a majority enrollment of Asian or Asian American students, three Latinx students, two White students and one Black student.³ There were fourteen students who completed the class in total. The article is written from the perspective of three individuals who were involved in the course: the professor, B (they/them), and two pre-service teachers who took the course as students, Saul (he/him) and Syd (she/they). The article begins with statements of our own positionality and brief overviews of the core theories utilized in the course redesign. Following this, B explains the course goals and design, as well as some of the key assignments the pre-service teachers were required to complete. Next, the article transitions to experiences of the two pre-service teachers, Syd and Saul, who completed the course as students. The article ends with broad suggestions for teacher educators to consider as they work to implement the pedagogical theories and models discussed throughout this article.

Positionality

The identities and experiences we carry as authors are foundational elements to our engagement with this course redesign and its analysis. Our paths may have crossed to form a shared experience at this particular point in time, but our lives up until and surrounding our experiences in and with the MPP class have differed, and thus we bring different perspectives to the analysis in this article.

Saul (he/him) is a Latino, straight, Nicaraguan-American who was born in the USA yet raised in Nicaragua. He returned to the USA at the age of 13 as a multilingual learner in racially and ethnically diverse urban schools where he graduated as Valedictorian. He is currently studying to earn a Bachelor of Science in Mathematics Education at an ethnically and racially diverse university in New York City. He worked as a tutor for America Reads at a K-8 school in New York City, and is currently a student teacher at Landmark High School in New York City teaching Algebra 2. Saul hopes to continue working in urban schools after graduation. Saul's experiences and identity have influenced his embrace of nontraditional and liberatory ways of teaching mathematics.

Syd (she/they) is a White queer student. As a student, they deal with a learning disability in the form of dyslexia, paired with ADHD. All of their primary and secondary schooling took place at predominately White institutions (PWIs) in a majority White town. At the time of writing she was getting their Bachelor of Science in Mathematics Education at a racially and ethnically diverse university in New York City, and had been working in the field as a tutor for America Reads/America Counts for the past two years. They were student teaching at a public middle school in New York City. Her goal was to teach middle school math in New York City after graduation. At the time of revision, she is employed at a public middle school in the Lower East Side, teaching 6th grade math. Syd touches on their background in their reflection, noting the cultural shift that occurred during their transition from traditional primary and secondary schooling, to a progressive post-secondary environment. All of their identities factor into their thinking around education, and thus are necessary to disclose.

² Throughout the manuscript we will vary the order of the terms “ethnically” and “racially” diverse, so as not to place emphasis on one over the other.

³ Throughout this paper, we capitalize the words “Black,” “Brown,” and “White” intentionally. We write “Black” and “Brown” with a capital “B”, to acknowledge that these two words do not only signify color, but the unique racial identities and histories of struggle and resilience of Black and Brown communities in the United States and globally. We intentionally capitalize the “W” in “White” in order to name White as a race and to call attention to White folk's need to grapple with their race, considering how it functions within our society and political institution. This choice of capitalization is aligned with style recommendations from organizations such as The National Association of Black Journalists (2020).

B (they/them) is a Latinx, disabled, neurodivergent, queer educator. They have over 15 years of experience in both formal and informal PK-20 educational settings including - private, public, and charter schools, after and summer school programs, in schools serving urban, suburban, and rural populations, in predominantly White and ethnically and racially diverse institutions, and in “single sex”⁴ and co-educational settings. They currently work as a teacher educator at a public institution in California, while also serving as an education consultant and co-running a professional development organization dedicated to anti-racist, queer, and other radical pedagogies, which they co-founded in 2021. They also created and run an online STEM enrichment program for 2SLGBTQIA+ youth.⁵ All of these experiences and identities were influential to B’s motives and ideas for reimagining the MPP course, especially that of stepping outside the traditional views of what we would see in a course focused on mathematical proof and proving. These experiences have also influenced their desire to write with students to understand the impact of this redesign on their understanding of what it means to teach and learn mathematics.

Teacher Education and Pedagogical Theories

In the field of teacher education, we are exposed to a number of academic theories and models such as disability justice, anti-racist pedagogy, queer pedagogy, and abolitionist teaching. Over the years, many of us have learned to infuse bits and pieces of each of these theories into our own teaching to create a more liberatory and equitable mathematics experience for PK-20 mathematics students, as well as the pre- and in-service teachers with whom we work. Something that many of us struggle with, however, is how to make these theories come alive for in-service and pre-service teachers themselves, connecting theory to practice (Broekkamp & van Hout-Wolters, 2007; Kennedy, 1997; Flores, 2016) so they might look back and say “oohhhh, so THAT is what (insert pedagogy/theory/model) actually looks like.” It is one thing to talk about and understand a theory or model of education, but an entirely different matter to understand how to *apply* that model to your own instruction, especially if you have never experienced education in that way before (see, for example, Fasching-Varner & Seriki, 2012; Nolan, 2014).

The MPP course discussed in this article was designed to help students understand these theories by engaging in an explicit unearthing of the above listed academic theories and models. Before we discuss that process, however, we will provide readers with a brief overview of each of these educational theories and models.

Abolitionist Teaching

Abolitionist teaching, a qualifier that intentionally mirrors the abolition of slavery (Sanchez, 2023), aims to dismantle the oppressive systems that exist in the school system and create better, safer, and more loving systems. Rather than viewing these oppressive systems through the lens of restructuring or reformation, abolitionists aim for liberation from these systems, liberation which cannot come in the form of “tweaks” (Love, 2019). Abolitionist teachers look at systems present through a race-based lens, centering “dark folx,” a term scholar, educator, and leading voice in abolitionist teaching Bettina Love (2019) uses to encompass and recenter all students of color,

⁴ Here, “single sex” is put in quotation marks because B recognizes that sex is not a binary concept. Additionally, the school is described as single sex, rather than single gender, because at the time, the school had not yet begun a conversation about granting trans women admittance.

⁵ While many folx may be familiar with the LGBT or LGBTQ+ acronym, B uses the 2SLGBTQIA+ acronym to honor that those of indigenous two-spirit (2S) identities existed on this continent long before the other queer and trans identities in this acronym. Additionally, the I, for Intersex and A for asexual/aromantic identities are included in the acronym to honor that these identities are all too often left out of conversations about queer and trans identity.

while simultaneously disregarding typical gendered norms - an intentional decision that encompasses the destruction of norms that exist within abolitionist teaching. Abolitionist teachers highlight how dark folx are forgotten in curriculum, targeted at higher rates for discipline and arrest, and not given space to succeed. As Sanchez (2023) notes, while Love does not advocate for a monolithic idea of instruction through abolitionist teaching, her ideas center around action. This looks like creating spaces bell hooks (1997) coined as “homeplace”, which Love (2019, p. 63) describes as a place where “[B]lack folx truly matter to each other, where souls are nurtured, comforted, and fed ... a community, typically led by women, where White power and the damages done by it are healed by loving Blackness and restoring dignity.” When speaking directly to White educators who identify as abolitionist teachers, the work is put upon those educators to surpass the role of an ally and become a co-conspirator, a role which requires you to put yourself, your power, and your privilege on the line to fight against these systems, rather than simply acknowledging their existence. Abolitionist teaching is the ongoing fight against oppression and the struggle for freedom, both inside and outside the classroom.

Anti-Racist Pedagogy

Anti-racist pedagogy is a method of instruction that actively attempts to challenge and dismantle racism within schools. It is based on *freedom dreaming* (Love, 2019; Spaulding et al., 2021), which is a creative, confident and unapologetic process of envisioning and striving for a new reality that counters White supremacy, racism and colonialism in all its forms. Most importantly, anti-racist pedagogy is grounded in delight (Spaulding et al., 2021). According to Spaulding and colleagues (2021), “If Black joy does not exist in a school, then the school is racist” (p. 9). It is in having a deep appreciation, respect, acknowledgement, and acceptance of Black and Brown people, cultures, and identities that a classroom and/or school can educate students holistically and effectively. Pedagogically, this can be achieved in several ways. White teachers must have a personal conversation with themselves regarding their privilege and inherent racism in order to interrogate such perceptions. Anti-racist teachers educate themselves and their students about the horrors of racism, engage in healing, work actively to fight against any policies or employees that are racist, and revise the curriculum where needed to reflect the cultures and needs of Black and Brown students (Spaulding et al., 2021). The ultimate goal being to cause positive academic outcomes for Black and Brown students so their futures are fortunate and rewarding.

Disability Justice

Disability justice is a movement that strives to give autonomy, voice, and liberation to disabled people (i.e., *crips*⁶) who are Black and Brown and/or queer and trans. Disability justice pedagogy is an intersectional, anti-racist, and decolonial method to guide academic studies so that Black and Brown and/or queer and trans crips are centered in the curriculum and given ample opportunities for their voices to be heard, acknowledged, appreciated, and accepted. This goes beyond teaching one-time, temporary units that pertain to the above mentioned group, and instead means infusing the curriculum and daily classroom experience with acknowledgement and appreciation of the Black and Brown and/or queer and trans crips’ voices and experiences. This runs counter to the White supremacist, racist, capitalist and decolonial views that define most public schools, so endeavors at disability justice pedagogy will have a lasting impact on students and the overall school culture. As Kafai (2021) states, “With this type of education, we can work together to create a most loving and willfully defiant world where all our bodyminds thrive together in movement”

⁶ The disability justice movement aims to reclaim terms that were used to degrade disabled people in the past. As such, words like *crip* and *disabled* were reclaimed to denote positivity and strength, rather than negativity and weakness.

(p. 61). As teacher educators, pre-service teachers, and in-service teachers, attempting to employ disability justice pedagogy in our classrooms will serve as a catalyst to normalize and equalize the variety of voices that make up the American public school system.

Queer Pedagogy

Queer pedagogy is the application of queer theory to pedagogical practices. What queer theory aims to do is to disrupt the social norm, not by adding queer people to it, but to challenge it as a whole. Although the word queer has many different associations, many of them being negative in the past, today queer can be acknowledged as an all encompassing, if somewhat over simplified, umbrella term representing all gender and sexuality minorities, i.e., anyone who does not identify as cisgendered and straight (Dubbs, 2016). Incorporating queerness is not the same as ignoring it, rather understanding there is no right and moral way to live classified by sexuality, sex, or gender. Queer pedagogy focuses on bringing these identities to the center to showcase and understand the experiences of queer people, especially those that are Black, Brown, disabled, or otherwise underrepresented. It involves learning and acknowledging how being queer interacts with your experience both inside and outside the classroom, and how keeping queerness separate from the class, as so many would like to do, is an act of violence that only further perpetuates the violence that queer people experience. Additionally, queer theory and pedagogy work to push back on *all* normative categorizations or dichotomous understandings, even those that extend beyond queer and trans identities (Waid, 2020). As noted by Mendick (2006), mathematics is a field riddled with binaries/dichotomies such as “hard/easy,” “abstract/concrete,” “fast/slow”, “naturally able/badly prepared,” and so on (pp. 131-132).

In addition to these normative categorizations and dichotomies identified by Mendick, what counts as proof and proving in mathematics is also a site of normative understanding to be troubled in mathematics. As noted by Hersch (1993), mathematicians often view the role of proof as not only a form of verification of a conjecture, but also an explanation of “*why* it is correct” (p. 390). On the contrary, when we think of real world contexts, things are not definite and possibly cannot be verified; they can be messy, convoluted, and open ended. So does this mean that real world contexts cannot be a site of mathematical proof? According to Hodgson and Riley (2001, p. 724), “proof and real-world problem solving are typically considered to be separate and distinct endeavors”. In other words, using real world context as a site of mathematical proving is a way of disrupting the perceived dichotomy between the two and as a means to support the development of axiomatic thinking that underpins proof and proving, as well as to support the development of mathematical concepts in meaningful ways. Hodgson and Riley (2001) have noted a similar line of thinking in regards to the use of real-world contexts as a site of proof and have stated,

[O]ur experience has been that real-world problems supply an important ingredient that seems to be missing from typical classroom instruction on proof. As such, real-world problems may actually be one of the most effective contexts for introducing and eliciting proof. Real-world problems are commonly used as vehicles to introduce or deepen students' understanding of mathematical concepts and relationships. (p. 724)

From this discussion, we have illustrated that queer pedagogy requires attention to that which is not given attention, in mathematics and beyond. You must consider different perspectives, and the impact on what you are doing, especially when using a curriculum that was not made with queer people in mind, or any other people whose identities fall outside the normative, White, able-bodied, Western views upon which our current mathematics curriculum is constructed. Dubbs (2016) beautifully sums up the heart of queer pedagogy by stating, “In addition to simply including queer examples, however, mathematics education researchers should continue to question the

nature and boundaries of mathematics itself to challenge the notion of mathematics as fixed, neutral, and culture free” (p. 1046).

Designing the Mathematical Proof and Proving Course

Course Description, Demographics, and Implicit and Explicit Goals

In Spring of 2023, I was asked to adjunct a Mathematical Proof and Proving (MPP) course at a racially and ethnically diverse university in New York City. When I was approached to teach this course, I was hesitant to accept. I preferred teaching pedagogy courses at the teacher preparation level and had horrible flashbacks of constructing “rigorous” (read: rigid, cold, boring) mathematical proofs in my own early teacher preparation. These flashbacks triggered my imposter syndrome (e.g., Leyva, 2022) and I began asking, “Should I really be the one to teach this course?” Ultimately, my reservations are *why* I agreed to teach the course. After approximately 15 years in the field, I had enough distance and understanding to know that MPP did not *have* to be experienced the way I experienced it in my early teacher training and I was determined to find another way to expose pre-service teachers to something different. But how might I go about such a task?

First and foremost, I wanted to underpin the course with a number of foundational pedagogical models that would outline the liberatory teaching methods we often talk about in teaching methods courses, but rarely allow students to see in action, much less experience themselves. In particular, I was interested in exposing students to methods of queer pedagogy, abolitionist teaching, anti-racist pedagogy, and disability justice. I also wanted to expose students to a mix of abstract mathematical proof and proving techniques and examples that showed them that we can use mathematical proving and argumentation techniques to help make sense of our world. Finally, I wanted to witness how students' understanding of mathematical proof and proving, as well as the pedagogical theories discussed above, would evolve throughout the course.

With this in mind, I landed on three overarching student learning goals (SLGs) for the course (Waid, 2023a, p. 19):

1. Students will engage in mathematical problem solving on three problem sets, tackling formal mathematical proofs pertaining to number theory and abstract algebra.
2. Students will use mathematical argumentation to construct relevant arguments pertaining to two social contexts, to be determined according to student interests.
3. Students will learn, through modeling, the basic principles of [and] practical ways to engage in an anti-racist, abolitionist, queer, and disability justice oriented pedagogy.

The rationale for each of these goals and how they were executed are elaborated upon in the sections that follow.

Designing the Course SLG 1

Goal 1 was particularly important to the mathematics education department chair, who, in our initial discussions of the course, communicated that MPP had been designed as a primer course of sorts. The department had found that many of their undergraduate mathematics education students, who were required to take the majority of their mathematics content courses outside of the School of Education and with the mathematics department in the School of Sciences, would ultimately drop their mathematics education major as a result of struggling in their mathematics content courses offered by the mathematics department. The MPP course was one mechanism the department had developed to better support undergraduate mathematics education majors in transitioning to the mathematics department for the remainder of their content courses. It was

considered a mathematics content course, but designed specifically for pre-service teachers pursuing a mathematics education degree.

I pondered this course goal for a long time, trying to determine the nature of *why* the mathematics content courses within the mathematics department were serving as a gatekeeper for aspiring mathematics teachers. From what I could gather, much of it had to do with the fast paced nature of the courses, as well as many students feeling they needed to learn mathematics on their own by reading the course textbook, something they likely had never had to do in their PK-12 mathematics experiences. Added to that, their undergraduate mathematics professors were not explicitly supporting them to develop the skill of reading *about* mathematics and applying the concepts they were reading about. For this reason, I decided to infuse problem sets throughout the course, which would rely on a flipped model of instruction. Each problem set would contain at least one “Pause and Learn” section and then a “Now You Try” section that would follow it. The problem sets themselves introduced students to mathematical concepts and proving techniques they would learn in a college level abstract algebra or number theory course.

I also knew that providing this flipped model of learning through problem sets would not be enough on its own. Without thoughtful implementation, the problem sets ran the risk of simply replicating students’ undergraduate mathematics professors’ model of making them learn on their own without supporting them in making sense of the mathematical texts. To mitigate such a risk, I determined that I would begin every class with a fifteen to twenty minute collaborative work session, where students could work with their peers to make sense of the “Pause and Learn” portions of their problem sets and apply their new knowledge to the “Now You Try” sections. I was also available during this time to aid students in their sense making of the text. In addition to the time allotted for collaborative work, I also set aside one class period before the due date of the problem set for students to provide one another with feedback on their peers’ problem set assignments. On these days, students would pair up and read each others’ completed problem sets and formatively assess each problem on their classmate’s problem set, using a scoring sheet with the rubric depicted in Figure 1.

For problems that were procedural or fact/question based, students simply marked off for correctness; whereas for problems that were more involved, requiring some sort of mathematical proof and problem solving, they used the problem solving rubric we collaboratively created as an evaluation tool during our first unit of instruction, shown in Figure 1. The scoring sheet also provided space for students to provide one another with written feedback to elaborate on their scoring. Given that some may find it easier to verbally convey feedback, students were instructed they could choose to use this space, or they might verbally express their feedback to their peers as their peers took notes.

Article continues on the next page.

MPP PROBLEM SET PROBLEMS RUBRIC				
KEY TRAITS	4	3	2	1
"UNDERSTANDING OF THE PROBLEM" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 1, SCLAE 1).	"THE STUDENT DEMONSTRATES IN-DEPTH UNDERSTANDING OF THE RELEVANT CONCEPTS &/OR PROCESSES" (KENTUCKY DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, 1992, LEVEL 5.)	"THE STUDENT DEMONSTRATES UNDERSTANDING OF MAJOR CONCEPTS EVEN THOUGH [THEY] OVERLOOK OR MISUNDERSTANDS SOME LESS IMPORTANT IDEAS OR DETAILS" (KENTUCKY DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, 1992, LEVEL 4).	"THE STUDENT DEMONSTRATES THAT THERE ARE GAPS IN THEIR CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING" (KENTUCKY DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, 1992, LEVEL 3).	"DIDN'T UNDERSTAND ENOUGH TO GET STARTED OR MAKE PROGRESS" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 1, SCLAE 1).
COMMUNICATION (GENERAL)	"GIVES A COMPLETE RESPONSE WITH A CLEAR, UNAMBIGUOUS EXPLANATION &/OR DESCRIPTION; MAY INCLUDE AN APPROPRIATE & COMPLETE DIAGRAM; COMMUNICATES EFFECTIVELY TO THE IDENTIFIED AUDIENCE; PRESENTS STRONG SUPPORTING ARGUMENTS WHICH ARE LOGICALLY SOUND & COMPLETE; MAY INCLUDE EXAMPLES & COUNTER-EXAMPLES" (LANE, 1993, LEVEL 4 COMMUNICATION).	"GIVES A FAIRLY COMPLETE RESPONSE WITH REASONABLY CLEAR EXPLANATIONS OR DESCRIPTIONS; MAY INCLUDE A NEARLY COMPLETE, APPROPRIATE DIAGRAM; GENERALLY COMMUNICATES EFFECTIVELY TO THE IDENTIFIED AUDIENCE; PRESENTS SUPPORTING ARGUMENTS WHICH ARE LOGICALLY SOUND BUT MAY CONTAIN SOME MINOR GAPS" (LANE, 1993, LEVEL 3 COMMUNICATION).	"MAKES SIGNIFICANT PROGRESS TOWARDS COMPLETION OF THE PROBLEM, BUT THE EXPLANATION OR DESCRIPTION MAY BE SOMEWHAT AMBIGUOUS OR UNCLEAR; MAY INCLUDE A DIAGRAM WHICH IS FLAWED OR UNCLEAR; COMMUNICATION MAY BE SOMEWHAT VAGUE OR DIFFICULT TO INTERPRET; & ARGUMENTS MAY BE INCOMPLETE OR MAY BE BASED ON A LOGICALLY UNSOUND PREMISE" (LANE, 1993, LEVEL 2 COMMUNICATION).	"HAS SOME SATISFACTORY ELEMENTS BUT MAY FAIL TO COMPLETE OR MAY OMIT SIGNIFICANT PARTS OF THE PROBLEM; EXPLANATION OR DESCRIPTION MAY BE MISSING OR DIFFICULT TO FOLLOW; MAY INCLUDE A DIAGRAM WHICH INCORRECTLY REPRESENTS THE PROBLEM SITUATION, OR DIAGRAM MAY BE UNCLEAR AND DIFFICULT TO INTERPRET." (LANE, 1993, LEVEL 1 COMMUNICATION).
MPP PROBLEM SET PROBLEMS RUBRIC CONT				
KEY TRAITS	4	3	2	1
"HOW STUDENT SOLVED PROBLEM" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 1, SCLAE 2).	"APPROACH WAS EFFICIENT OR SOPHISTICATED" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 4, SCLAE 2).	"APPROACH WOULD WORK FOR THE PROBLEM" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 3, SCLAE 2).	"APPROACH ONLY LEADS TO SOLVING PART OF THE PROBLEM" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 2, SCLAE 2).	"APPROACH DIDN'T WORK" (VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, N.D., LEVEL 1, SCLAE 2).
COMMUNICATION (TOULMIN)	OVER 90% OF THE CLAIMS, DATA, & WARRANTS IN THE ARGUMENT ARE IDENTIFIABLE, SOUND, & CLEAR.	70-90% OF THE CLAIMS, DATA, & WARRANTS ARE IDENTIFIABLE, SOUND, & CLEAR.	40-70% OF THE CLAIMS, DATA, & WARRANTS ARE IDENTIFIABLE, SOUND, & CLEAR.	LESS THAN 40% OF THE CLAIMS, DATA, & WARRANTS ARE IDENTIFIABLE, SOUND, & CLEAR.
<p>PROBLEMS WHERE YOU ARE ASKED TO LIST THINGS LEARNED/QUESTIONS WILL BE SCORED FOR COMPLETION. A SCORE OF "0" IS ASSIGNED FOR ANY PROBLEM THAT IS SKIPPED ENTIRELY</p>				
MPP PROBLEM SET PROBLEMS RUBRIC REFERENCES				
<p>KENTUCKY DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (1992). 211 KENTUCKY HOLISTIC SCORING RUBRIC FOR GRADE 12 MATH. HTTPS://WEB.NJIT.EDU/~RONKOWIT/PRESENTATIONS/RUBRICS/SAMPLES/MATH_PROBSOLV_CHICAGO.PDF</p> <p>LANE, S, (1993) THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT INSTRUMENT. EDUCATIONAL MEASUREMENT: ISSUES AND PRACTICE, 12(2) 16-23.</p> <p>VERMONT DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (N.D.) 207 VERMONT MATH PROBLEM SOLVING CRITERIA. HTTPS://WEB.NJIT.EDU/~RONKOWIT/PRESENTATIONS/RUBRICS/SAMPLES/MATH_PROBSOLV_CHICAGO.PDF</p>				

Figure 1. Problem Solving Rubric collaboratively created by the MPP community.

NOTE. We ended up dropping the Toulmin analysis (last row) of this rubric half way through the course because I felt students were getting too caught up in identifying what the warrant, data, claim, and backing elements were in their proofs, rather than the overarching idea that each claim had data, a warrant, and sufficient backing to support it. This should be taken as a reflection of my own limited understanding of Toulmin and not any limitation of the overall methods presented by Katz et al. (2022).

In selecting these design elements for SLG 1 (flipped instruction, collaborative work time, peer feedback in forms that felt comfortable), I was also mindful in thinking through the connections between these choices and the liberatory pedagogical models that I wanted to underpin the course. In particular, I sought to lean into the disability justice and anti-racist practice of *hard caring*. Antrop-González and De Jesús (2006), discussed the distinction between hard and soft caring. They noted that in White feminist frameworks, teachers enact a soft caring, especially in relation to their students of color, because they pity the circumstances of their students, leading them to lower their expectations for those students. Teachers enact a hard caring when they maintain high expectations for all students, regardless of their circumstances, while fostering authentic, and supportive relationships with those students and providing them with tools to help them achieve those high expectations. Such teachers honor their students' circumstances, without lowering their expectations. This was my goal with the problem sets. I wanted to acknowledge that it is hard to learn abstract mathematical concepts on your own, but it is still a skill that needs to be acquired to succeed in their university mathematics courses. In essence, I was seeking to teach students to “play the game called mathematics” (Gutiérrez, 2009, p. 6), but supporting them in this practice by providing class time to collaboratively discuss and synthesize the learning that they were expected to do independently for their problem sets. This provided a scaffold to help students achieve the high expectations I maintained for them.

Gutiérrez has noted that simply teaching students to play the game is not enough, because “students must also be able to change the game” (p. 6) in order to transform mathematics. My desire for my students to be able to “change the game,” especially as future teachers, is why I enacted some of the other pedagogical decisions in relation to SLGs 2 and 3. I wanted students to see that mathematical proof did not need to be taught in such an abstract, disconnected way, but could instead be used as a tool to critically engage with their world.

Designing for Course SLG 2

Goal 2 was the heart of my thinking on how to redesign the MPP course to meet the needs of the departments (as described in the SLG 1 discussion), as well as my own desire to get students to rethink what it means to learn and teach mathematics and to engage in mathematical argumentation and proof—i.e., to “change the game” (Gutiérrez, 2009, p. 6). As such, I envisioned the course as being sectioned into three units, as shown in Figure 2. During those three units, students would also be working on their problem sets (those discussed as part of SLG 1), which they would then bring to class at the conclusion of the unit, to receive feedback from their peers. They would use the feedback from their peers to revise their problem sets before submitting the assignment the following week, once we had begun the next unit of instruction.

Article continues on the next page.

Figure 2. Overview of MPP Units of Instruction.

The first unit would be focused on building a shared understanding of what we needed from ourselves and our peers to bring our best selves to the teaching and learning of mathematics (i.e., setting community agreements), as well as building a basic understanding of what counts as mathematical proof and proving. This unit spanned four weeks of our course, which met for one hour and forty minutes, once a week, during which we spent two class periods identifying and refining our community agreements via a method I have described elsewhere (Waid, 2023b; Fletcher & Waid, 2024) and two class periods introducing students to Pólya's (1945) four step process to problem solving and proving in action. As part of this introduction, students read Yoshinobu's (2003) article "Mathematics, Politics and Greenhouse Gas Intensity: An Example of Using Pólya's Problem-Solving Strategy," as well as the student perspective from Katz, Thoren, and Hernandez's (2022) paper "Why Should that Convince Me?: Teaching Toulmin Analysis Across the Curriculum." We then utilized our learning from these articles to build, in small groups, mathematical proofs for the following statement, inspired from a tweet from Enlow (2021), "It is possible to get every positive integer by adding and/or subtracting only 5s and 8s." Students then used both informal and formal (Toulmin) methods of analysis to critique one another's proofs. To conclude the unit, students used their experiences of collaboratively developing proofs, as well as knowledge gained from viewing several examples of various problem solving rubrics (Chicago Public Schools Bureau of Student Assessment, n.d.) to develop the problem solving rubric shown in Figure 1.

The second unit was an in depth exploration of wealth and racial inequality, which is one of the top two social issues students indicated an interest in on a survey I gave them on the first day of the course. Throughout the unit students engaged with and discussed various print and multimedia sources to develop their understanding of income inequality and the NYC Baby Bonds

initiative that had been developed as one means to address such inequities (e.g., TED-Ed, 2022; Coates, 2014; Bernard, 2021; Kotler, n.d.). In addition to these sources, students explored data from the US Census Bureau (2021a; 2021b; 2021c; 2021d; 2021e; 2021f; 2021g; 2021h; 2021i; 2021j) including the Gini Index of most of NYC's boroughs (Bronx, Brooklyn, Manhattan, and Queens, specifically⁷), the median income of all of NYC, the median income of the given boroughs, as well as 2021 median income data for 2SLGBTQIA+ communities analyzed by the Human Rights Campaign (2022), and research on generational wealth for Black, White, and Latinx families (Bhutta et al., 2020).⁸ Students used this data to create models to predict how much we might expect an NYC resident of given identities (e.g., a Queens resident who is a Latinx, queer, woman) to make over a period of twenty years, as well as to determine how long it would take for the given individual to be able to afford the down payment for an apartment in their given borough. They spent time looking through each other's work and comparing the expected median wealth accumulation of individuals of the particular identities they had selected. All of these investigations (mathematical and otherwise) were then used as a basis to create a mathematical argument as to whether they believed the NYC Baby Bonds initiative was enough to achieve its stated goals - namely to alleviate some of the wealth disparities in NYC by providing greater access to higher education.

The final unit, also selected from the students' interest survey at the start of the term, was one on food insecurity. We began with a general exploration of the issue, its prevalence in NYC and what currently and historically has been done to address the issue (e.g. NYC's FRESH program, City of New York, n.d.; the Black Panthers' Free Breakfast program, Blakemore, 2018). As part of this exploration, we watched and discussed a local news broadcast that gave an overview of food access, food deserts, and food swamps in NYC (CBS New York, 2022). We then used the newscasts discussions of "healthy, affordable food" to begin parsing out our thoughts about what qualified as healthy and affordable food. For example, would building a Whole Foods, which has healthy food, but is expensive, be considered a solution to the issue of food access in a low income area like Central Harlem? How about a high income area like the Upper East Side? NYC in particular has a lot of bodegas and corner stores - do those work to address the food access issue? Throughout these discussions we collaboratively developed working definitions of the types of stores that would be classified as offering affordable, healthy choices - mainly supermarkets and grocery stores. We also decided on two other food establishment classifications that did not fit the criteria of offering healthy, affordable food access, 1) bodegas/convenience stores/gas stations/corner stores and 2) restaurants and fast food. After exploring the issue and determining definitions, students selected an NYC zip code and, using Desmos, as well as the New York State Food Inspection Website (n.d.) and income data from unit 2, students created a map and began plotting the locations of food establishments in their zip code, as well as labeling them as a grocery store or supermarket, a bodega or similar establishment, or a restaurant or fast food establishment. Finally, students used this information to create a mathematical argument as to whether a food desert existed in their selected zip code, thus making it eligible for a NYC FRESH program location. These three units were key in my attempt to have students experience mathematics as useful, worthwhile, and a tool that can be used to understand and advocate for change.

⁷ We omitted the borough of Staten Island because none of the students taught or lived in Staten Island.

⁸ This was included to provide a more intersectional look at wealth distribution and to discuss what assumptions we would be making (namely, the independence of identities), if we used the given data to determine the median income of, for example, a Black, queer, disabled woman and how that would impact the accuracy of the answers we yielded.

As stated in my discussion of SLG 1, in selecting the above described design elements for SLG 2, I was also mindful in thinking through the connections between these choices and the liberatory pedagogical models that I wanted to underpin the course. In addition to modeling to students how they might teach mathematical concepts in ways that “change the game” (Gutiérrez, 2009, p. 6) of mathematics to allow their students to “read and write the world with mathematics” (Gutstein, 2016), my decision to allow students to *choose* the social issues they desired to explore (wealth inequality and food insecurity) was a means of resisting the normative idea of the teacher as the source of authority in the classroom. Such a decentering of authority aligns with an abolitionist pedagogy because it works to dismantle the oppressive structures of “authority” that often come at the expense of Black and Brown children (Love, 2019; González, 2024). This decentering of authority also relates to queer pedagogy in that it disrupts a social norm and the binary of power that exists within the dichotomy of student/teacher. Disrupting such binary and normative notions are at the heart of a queer pedagogy (Waid, 2020).

In addition to allowing students to choose the focus of these units, I also provided them with choice in how they constructed their final mathematical arguments in these contexts – making social media infographics, writing to their representatives, etc. – as well as choice in the NYC boroughs they explored and a choice in the format they might respond to reading and mathematical prompts in their Mathematical Argumentation Journals, a reflective journal that they were required to keep throughout the semester. These elements of choice are essential to enacting a Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which centers on the principle of providing students multiple means of 1) engagement, 2) representation and 3) learning (CAST, 2018). By enacting UDL in these ways, my goal was to honor the disability justice principle that “all bodies have strengths and needs that must be met” (Sins Invalid, 2020, para. 5) and allow students flexibility to tap into their strengths, while also attending to their needs.

Outside of these elements of choice, my design of these two units also intentionally centered aspects of community joy and resistance, especially Black joy and resistance, key elements of antiracist and abolitionist pedagogies. While it is commonplace for social justice lessons to be focused on issues that impact historically marginalized communities, abolitionist and anti-racist scholar Bettina Love (2021) has argued that such a focus is not anti-racist. In Love’s words,

Professional development and curriculum focused on anti-racism cannot just be consumed with Black people’s pain and trauma. That’s not anti-racism. That’s a class on power, privilege, and violence. Anti-racism is showing Black people’s lives, art, music, histories, and cultural means of resistance, survival, abolition, and Black joy. It’s showing Black people’s humanity. (Love, 2021, p. 155)

Throughout the two units, I sought to center this perspective by focusing on ways that Black, Brown, queer, trans, and disabled folx have organized, and engaged in mutual aid and resistance to address the issues facing their communities. For example, Black resistance was highlighted in discussions of food insecurity by discussing the mutual aid initiatives that were spearheaded by the Black Panthers and the Young Lords, such as the free breakfast program and free health clinic initiative.

Finally, my decision to focus on real world contexts as a site of mathematical proof was a decision aligned with queer pedagogy’s demand that we interrogate and trouble binaries and dichotomies (Mendick, 2006; Waid, 2020). As noted in the discussion of queer pedagogy at the start of this article, there exists a commonly perceived dichotomy between the proof and real world contexts (Hodgson & Riley, 2001). By using real world contexts as a site of mathematical proof and proving, I sought to trouble, or “queer” this dichotomy in my coursework and in my students’ minds.

Designing for Course SLG 3

Goal 3 stemmed from my knowledge that this class was one composed of pre-service teachers who needed to not only be introduced to what anti-racist, abolitionist, queer, and disability justice oriented pedagogy was, but also what they looked like in action. To help them better conceptualize this, I also felt it was essential for students to begin understanding *why* I designed the course in the way I had, as well as the way various course elements were connected to the given pedagogies and models. To have students begin their “peek behind the curtain” and see how these elements were present in the course, I included information on my course syllabus outlining each of the discussed pedagogies and then a “Theory into Practice” section that discussed how specific practices and assignments for the course aligned with the theories, in a similar fashion as I have outlined in the discussions of how SLG 1 and SLG 2 are connected to the pedagogical theories underpinning the course. We also discussed these connections in class, as we encountered various connections to the theories. For example, the syllabus outlines how all of the pedagogical principles underpinning MPP can be seen in the course policy of adopting “crip time” (Kafer, 2013).

This policy relates to disability justice, abolitionist, queer, and anti-racist philosophies because it acknowledges how rigid deadlines center able-bodied, White supremacist, hetero/cisnormative, capitalistic, and colonial notions of productivity (Miller, 2020; Poole & Zerafa, 2023). My goal in enacting this policy was to disrupt such notions of productivity, to honor the bodily and societal constraints that are part of students' realities, and to move away from punitive grading measures that do not take into account “the cumulative effects of time spent managing mental health, chronic illness, ... stigmatized queer identities” (Miller, 2020, p. 14), as well as colonialism and White supremacy. Additionally, my use of crip time was grounded in a desire to extend grace with students, while also maintaining high expectations, which connects to the previously discussed notion of *hard caring* (Antrop-González and De Jesús, 2006). Throughout the course and syllabus, I communicated that even with my desire to extend grace I still maintained high expectations for their work on problem sets and course assignments, often relating back to this principle of hard caring and anti-racist pedagogy.

Two additional examples of how I sought to help students connect theory and practice during course discussions and in the syllabus (though there are others beyond this), come from my use of the “power with” model (e.g., Antrop-González and De Jesús, 2006) and infusing elements of mutual aid. In the syllabus, I describe the “power with” model as being illustrated when “the teacher works to decenter authority in the classroom, creating ‘power with’ students.” (Waid, 2023a, p. 12). I continue, stating,

In MPP, the ‘power with’ model shows up in the ways we will collaboratively generate rubrics and community agreements, the end of year conference in which you and I will assess your class participation collaboratively, and in the ways we will use our class generated community agreements to provide one another feedback that flows in all directions, including from you to me.

The use of the “power with” model is also closely related to the use of principles of mutual aid. Discussing this connection, I quote an article from the *The Activist History Review* (Jackson et al., 2020) which states,

Disability justice and mutual aid in the classroom reject expectations of ceaseless productivity by reallocating collective efforts to community building and solidarity among students and workers. Mutual aid informed by disability justice asserts that trade-offs [will not] always look exactly equivalent: they are based on the needs of each person, what they are able to provide, and are conscious of sometimes fluid power dynamics. (para. 5)

In the syllabus, I note that mutual aid shows up in many of the same practices that were discussed in the “power with” model, but also in my insistence that “opportunities to build community and check in on our social and emotional, as well as physical needs, are more important than covering content and being productive.” This was especially embodied in our weekly debriefs where students reflected on what they were thinking/feeling based on what has been discussed during that week’s class. In relation to this weekly debrief, the syllabus quotes something I have written elsewhere (Waid, 2023c),

[your] reflection can take whatever shape makes most sense to [you], meaning [you] can reflect on the content of what [you] learned (e.g., “I’m still struggling with...”, “I feel really good about...”), my pedagogy (e.g., “I really like the ___ strategy you used because ...”, “I didn’t find ___ strategy helpful because ...”), classroom dynamics (e.g., “I’m finding it hard to work with ___ because...”, “I worked well with ___ because..”, “I liked working alone on this assignment because...”, “I liked working in groups on this assignment because..”), [your] affect (e.g., “I was having a bad day today,” “I was struggling to pay attention because I didn’t sleep well last night”) or anything else [you] find relevant. (p. 44)

Illustrations of the “power with” and “mutual aid” models within the syllabus were also elaborated upon during class, with a discussion of how various elements relate to all four of the pedagogical theories underpinning the course. For example, collaboratively generated rubrics and community agreements relate to queer and abolitionist pedagogies because they resist normative ideas of who should have authority (González, 2024). These elements also relate to anti-racist pedagogy because they present opportunities to interrogate how White supremacy might show up in our ideas of what counts as “knowledge,” “appropriate” ways to demonstrate knowledge, and our understanding of terms like “respect” and “participation.” Similarly, the centering student wellness/needs over content (mutual aid), is an example of all of these pedagogical principles because it disrupts normative, ableist, and White supremacist notions inherent to a “banking model” of education, which is described by Freire (1970) as follows:

[E]ducation thus becomes an act of depositing, in which the students are the depositories and the teacher is the depositor. Instead of communicating, the teacher issues communiqués and makes deposits which the students patiently receive, memorize, and repeat. This is the ‘banking’ concept of education, in which the scope of action allowed to the students extends only as far as receiving, filling, and storing the deposits. (p. 72)

In addition to providing rationales and concrete examples of pedagogical practices such as those illustrated above, I knew that students would likely need a nudge to truly engage with these principles at the start and end of the year. For this reason, I created a start of semester assignment that had students read the syllabus and create a one-pager illustrating their key takeaways from reading the syllabus, especially in relation to the key theories illustrated, as well as two questions they still had after reading the syllabus. Figures 3 and 4 show the one pagers created by my coauthors, Syd and Saul, for this assignment.

Article continues on the next page.

Figure 3. Syllabus One-Pager created by Syd at the start of the semester.

Article continues on the next page.

Figure 4. Syllabus One-Pager created by Saul at the start of the semester.

Article continues on the next page.

I knew that, at this point, these theories would still be somewhat abstract for students because they had not yet experienced the course. For this reason, I also created an end of semester assignment that had students return to and reread the course syllabus and address the following questions (in a format of their choice) (Waid, 2023d, p. 1):

- Now that [you have] seen these pedagogical theories and practices (disability justice, anti-racist pedagogy, queer pedagogy, crip time, curb cut effect, abolitionist teaching, masking, UDL, mutual aid, hard caring, political clarity, “power with”, playing the game to change it, and collaboration) in action, how has your understanding of them evolved (or not) over the course of the semester? Provide specific examples of assignments, activities, or routines we used to support what [you are] saying.
- How have these pedagogical theories and practices contributed to your own developing understanding of mathematical proof and proving? Provide specific examples of assignments, activities, or routines we used to support what [you are] saying.
- How do you see yourself implementing these pedagogical theories and practices in your future classroom? Be specific. If you [do not] see yourself implementing them, explain why.

Pre-Service Teachers’ Experiences of the Course

In the section above, B explains the course goals and design, as well as some of the key assignments the pre-service teachers enrolled in the course were required to complete. In the sections that follow, we transition to the experiences of Saul and Syd, two pre-service teachers who completed the course as students and coauthors of this article.

Saul

At the start of the course, my initial belief about teaching mathematics in general was that a math teacher would utilize different pedagogical strategies which would enable the students to learn new mathematical terms and concepts. I basically believed that mathematics was a subject about numbers, formulas, and mathematical terminology. When I was being taught in school, my teachers focused on getting us through each unit of the math curriculum. One unit built upon another, and at the end of the unit, we would presumably be proficient in the subject whether it be Algebra, Geometry, Pre-Calculus, etc. In general, I have always loved working with numbers and math was my best subject, but I saw throughout the years students who loathed math because they struggled with it, and they would say that learning math was useless for their futures. In that sense, I realized that mathematics would be easier to teach to some students than others. I expected to encounter some resistance and dread from some students entering my mathematics class, depending upon their mathematical mindsets (Dweck, 2008; Boaler, 2016).

However, the MPP course units on *Wealth Inequality* and *Food Deserts* impacted my views greatly, especially in queering my views of what mathematics teaching could look like. In the *Wealth Inequality* unit, teaching mathematics was intertwined with the important issue of wealth inequality. In the *Food Deserts* unit, we used mathematics to reveal access to food availability based on what neighborhood a person lives in. Essentially, in both of these units we learned and applied mathematics to real world issues, providing us with an example of abolitionist, queer, and anti-racist pedagogical techniques which challenged my traditional systems of thought by opening my mind to liberatory ways of viewing humanity. What this did was very powerful for me as a future educator. I realized that I do not need to teach math in a vacuum focusing on numbers only. This

will help my future students because they will realize that math has a very important function in the world besides just calculating numbers for the sake of a class grade. It will be easier to convince my students who are weary of mathematics to get involved. Also, the discussion the units inspired were rich and critical to creating justice in the world, and solutions were presented and acted on (such as writing letters to politicians). This is relevant to all students' lives, and particularly to the students I will teach in economically disadvantaged schools who will need to be open to interrogating assumptions and then advocating for themselves and their communities.

Lastly, it was beneficial and quite powerful for me to write, design and illustrate in my Mathematical Argumentation Journal. Responding to texts and ideas on a blank page in any way I wanted freed me to deeply understand and analyze the content I was learning about, in a way that queered our learning experience (Mitchell et al., 2014). As I move into teaching someday, I would like to do variations of the *Wealth Inequality* and *Food Desert* units with my classes. Other ideas for units that I can develop on my own include *Government Expenditures: Where do your Taxes Go?*, *Lack of Access to Clean Water Worldwide*, and *Child Support Injustice*. Although I have always been excited to teach mathematics, now I am even more thrilled because I can teach students mathematics with a real world and social justice application in mind.

In class, we also did problem sets with abstract concepts. This was extremely beneficial to me as a future mathematics teacher, because it gave me the ability to learn in a context that was wholly foreign to me. As a result, I thought of new pedagogical methods that I could use in my classroom for students who are bewildered by new concepts. One method that I believe will be critical is to provide scaffolded support like my professor did. They coached us intensely as we were working in collaborative groups, asking probing questions, providing hints, suggestions, and direct instruction when we needed assistance. Additionally, there was plenty of group work and conversation, which helped us to see the “power with” model (Antrop-González and De Jesús, 2006) of mutual aid and its relation to disability justice (Sins Invalid, 2020), in action. I learned a lot from conversing with my peers and sharing ideas, and truthfully I might have been lost without having engaged in some of those conversations. Looking towards the future, if I am teaching a concept I know very well to my middle school students, I can now realize how in the dark students will be when they first start learning about that concept. I can put myself inside their minds a bit and use different methods to make them understand the material deeply, instead of teaching in an ineffective way that will only lead to a shallow and temporary understanding of the concepts.

Syd

As I mentioned intentionally in my positionality statement, I was raised and taught with primarily White peers. Experiencing the MPP class made me realize how much I have internalized about how classes should be run, and how uncomfortable I was with the transparent inclusion of abolitionist teaching, anti-racist pedagogy, disability justice, and queer pedagogy in the classroom. This is not to say that I disagreed with the inclusion; on the contrary I had been learning about the inclusion of these pedagogies, and I theoretically saw their importance and cheered for any teacher who chose to incorporate them. However, when I was on the receiving end, it did raise a multitude of different feelings for me. In all of the math classes I grew up taking, my expectation was that they would be impartial, which to me meant attending to numbers, functions, mathematical relations and nothing else. Despite all of the theory I had studied in the rest of my education classes, in practice I had not considered how these issues really interacted with mathematics, and how they would replace the structure that I had grown to be comfortable with. My discomfort with the inclusion of topics that I deemed irrelevant only grew with the seemingly total omission of numbers. While our curriculum did include some numbers, it was more reminiscent of how we would use numbers in a history class. Yes, they were there, but only as a way of description, not

as the lesson. Specifically, for our first problem set (problem set 1), I recall being so perplexed by the lack of equations and numbers I set up a meeting with B because I could not understand what the expectations could be with an assignment like that.

A realization came to me about the instability I felt about the course when I read *The Teaching Gap* by James Stigler and James Hiebert (2009). This book dissected and explained the implications of the 1995 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study, a study done to examine trends in students' mathematics and science achievement. A conclusion drawn from their research was that teaching is a cultural activity, which put into perspective that I was experiencing a culture shock. One of the tenets of abolitionist teaching, a pedagogy that was intentionally and abashedly included in our curriculum, is that in order for classrooms and the schooling system to thrive and for the students to succeed is the destruction of the current system and rebuilding new ones, rather than altering the existing systems (Love, 2019; 2020; Sanchez, 2023). This also connects to how queer pedagogy is aimed at disrupting normative processes (Dubbs, 2016; Mendick, 2006; Waid, 2020), and while we were made aware from the beginning that these pedagogies were involved with the conception of this course, this overhaul of every norm I had internalized throughout my fifteen years of schooling caused an intense cultural shock that left me unsure of my standing, doubtful of the course, and uncomfortable. One of our ongoing assignments through the semester, our Mathematical Argumentation Journal, showcased how these pedagogies interacted with what I thought should be the mathematical work. In this journal, we had assignments weekly which usually consisted of reading an article, such as one week in which we responded to Ta Nehisi Coates's (2014) article, "The Case for Reparations". The prompt asked us to name the main themes of this article, while also stating two questions we had. This article did contain what I thought of as mathematical elements through the financial aspect, but it mainly centered around the social implications. So again, the assignment was less rigorous than what I was used to and also had a lack of numbers. This was a stark contrast to the association I made with mathematics education through all of my previous experiences, including a higher level math class I was currently enrolled in, which was that for mathematics learning to be effective, not only does it have to be rigorous, which in itself is an implicative idea, but also that it has to be painful. And thus, when I was faced with a math class that was aimed at re-humanizing our mathematics experience (Gutiérrez, 2018), I was immediately doubtful. From the cultural perspective I had on mathematics, I thought it was not possible to be gaining knowledge from a math class if I did not dread going, or spend nights awake worrying that I was falling behind and would eventually fail, which is a frightening idea to have on an experience that every child has to go through.

This may sound as if I am being slightly superfluous with my description of a "typical" math class, but that has always been my experience in education. When it came to the hypothetical, I rejected notions of smartness, but through my lived experiences, I held to this notion of exclusivity that existed within mathematics. It wasn't until I had a transformative discussion with the head of the Mathematics Education department while struggling with a math class, that I understood the dichotomy that existed between my thoughts and my actions. I understood through this conversation that reading theory had not worked to change my mindset. Despite all the theory I had read and agreed with, when met with a professor who did give us grace, like incorporating crip time (Kafer, 2013) into class and giving leeway on all deadlines, I was startled. My mind went to how can we learn while being given leniency, even though I had always agreed in theory that it was so important to do that for my students. In my journey into being an educator, I have held at the utmost importance the idea that every student has the capability to learn and grow and digest material. But deep down, I still held the mindset that I was just not capable of learning some

material. I viewed my struggling in math as a failure of my character, rather than an issue of instruction or structure within the class.

Connecting back to the pedagogies included in the class, this is where I argue that no matter how much theory you engage with through readings or class discussions, unless you actively engage with it and create it outside the hypothetical, it cannot have the intended effect. This is an idea that Love (2019) argues through her call to go beyond ally into co-conspirator. As an ally, all I have to do is read the material, say I agree, and feel better about myself for being so progressive. Being a co-conspirator requires more work, effort, and most importantly, action. Through my different education classes, we had discussed in length anti-racist pedagogy and abolitionist teaching, pedagogies which call to White educators to look at the privilege and power they hold and go actively against it, while helping to reshape better systems. However, my first time seeing any form of restructuring, which was in MPP, I questioned its importance and its place. Up to this point, I had been confident in my allyship. While I never claimed to fully understand the injustices many students go through, nor do I think I will ever fully understand as it is something that will not impact me in the same way, I thought I put students experiences as the utmost importance, above my own comfortability of being silent and benefiting from these systems, but my resistance to change showed otherwise. As much as I thought I agreed with the ideals behind abolitionist teaching and queer pedagogy, meaning the destruction of the norms, I was fully comfortable in the normalcy and was unwelcome of change.

This only reinforces the fact that as much as you agree on paper, changing your mindset from what it has been conditioned to understand is hard work and goes beyond hypotheticals. It is uncomfortable, and you have to come to uncomfortable realizations about yourself. This was my first experience with seeing pedagogy such as anti-racist pedagogy, queer pedagogy, disability justice and abolitionist teaching reflected in my learning, and my initial reaction was to discount it. So while this class not only helped to broaden my acceptance and interest in what mathematics education can be structured as, it worked as a great educational opportunity for me to experience what being introduced to pedagogy in action looks like, especially as I hope to center them in my future classrooms. This class served as a transitional experience for me, where theory met action, where traditional American mathematics became not the only option, and where a desire for allyship in the classroom turned into a commitment to be a co-conspirator.

Overall Takeaways and Advice for Educators

Upon discussing Saul and Syd's overall experiences of the courses, we have begun to see the importance of mathematics teacher educators explicitly modeling the pedagogical theories they teach about in their courses. Both Syd and Saul had taken mathematics education courses prior to taking the MPP course. While those previous courses had emphasized disability justice, queer pedagogy, anti-racist pedagogy and abolitionist pedagogy, we see from Saul and Syd's discussion, they retained a belief that mathematics teaching was confined to the teaching of numbers, formulas, and abstract concepts. These sentiments are highlighted in the following statements made by Syd and Saul in the previous section:

SAUL: "At the start of the course, my initial belief about teaching mathematics in general was that a math teacher would utilize different pedagogical strategies which would enable the students to learn new mathematical terms and concepts. I basically believed that mathematics was a subject about numbers, formulas, and mathematical terminology."

SYD: “In all of the math classes I grew up taking, my expectation was that they would be impartial, which to me meant attending to numbers, functions, mathematical relations and nothing else. Despite all of the theory I had studied in the rest of my education classes, in practice I had not considered how these issues really interacted with mathematics, and how they would replace the structure that I had grown to be comfortable with. My discomfort with the inclusion of topics that I deemed irrelevant only grew with the seemingly total omission of numbers. While our curriculum did include some numbers, it was more reminiscent of how we would use numbers in a history class. Yes, they were there, but only as a way of description, not as the lesson.”

In Saul and Syd’s account, we find that though they had discussed disability justice, queer pedagogy, anti-racist pedagogy and abolitionist pedagogy in their mathematics courses, they had largely retained a traditional belief system about the nature of mathematics, while adopting more reform oriented, constructivist views about the teaching and learning of mathematics. Such belief systems may seem inconsistent, but previous studies (e.g., Raymond, 1997; Waid, 2018) have found similar cases in which teachers hold conflicting beliefs about the nature of mathematics and the teaching and learning of mathematics. In both of the cited studies, it was found that when an educator held student-centered, constructivist views about the teaching and learning of mathematics, but retained traditional views about the nature of mathematics (i.e., that it is algorithmic, centering on numbers and formulas), the teacher was more likely to engage in traditional teaching practices aligned with a “banking” (Freire, 1970) model of education.

Saul and Syd’s reflections in this article are consistent with the finding of these previous studies (Raymond, 1997; Waid, 2018). Their reflections also extend the findings of Raymond (1997) and Waid (2018), because while those studies were focused on beliefs about teaching and learning from a student-centered, constructivist lens, they situated mathematics teaching and learning in a more culture-neutral lens.⁹ Thus, Syd and Saul’s reflection have led us to conclude that a teachers’ belief about the nature of mathematics might also supersede the teachers belief about the importance of enacting liberatory pedagogies. This points to a need for mathematics teacher educators to engage in targeted interventions to (re)orient prospective teachers’ beliefs about the nature of mathematics, as these beliefs are the basis of how teachers will enact teaching practice (Ernest, 1989).

As we have seen in Saul and Syd’s reflections, (re)orienting their beliefs about the nature of mathematics was not possible until they were faced with a mathematics education course that *modeled* these pedagogies in action. The importance of such modeling is supported by research findings that K-12 teachers find it difficult to teach in ways that they have not experienced themselves (e.g., Nolan, 2014). However, mathematics teacher educators themselves have been found to struggle with breaking free from the traditional model of teaching they experienced as students (Nolan, 2022) and shifting towards more liberatory pedagogical models (Olawale et al., 2021). To combat this, we urge educators to engage in a process similar to the one that B adopted in redesigning the MPP course – beginning first with the models (disability justice) and pedagogical theories (anti-racist, queer, and abolitionist), then designing learning activities that are centered on those theories. Such a framing is also consistent with an abolitionist pedagogy, because it does not

⁹ The fact that B’s original dissertation approached mathematical learning in this way, also supports the narrative of Syd and Saul, as B was in the very early stages of learning about liberatory mathematics, without yet fully recognizing the disconnect between those theories and their beliefs, research, and practice. B now is of the belief that mathematics *cannot* be culture-neutral, but this journey took several years to make its way into their practice/research.

seek to take an already developed course and work to restructure or reform it. In the view of abolitionist educators, such attempts are futile, because the system itself is broken and cannot be fixed through “tweaks” (Love, 2019). From B’s experience, we have found that such an abolitionist effort of redesigning a course from the ground up, takes a considerable amount of time and effort. For this reason, we encourage teacher educators to do this work in collaboration, and to focus on redesigning one course at a time.

This idea that education cannot be fixed through “tweaks,” also brings to mind the following comment made by Saul in his reflection,

In general, I have always loved working with numbers and math was my best subject, but I saw throughout the years students who loathed math because they struggled with it, and they would say that learning math was useless for their futures. In that sense, I realized that mathematics would be easier to teach to some students than others. I expected to encounter some resistance and dread from some students entering my mathematics class, depending upon their mathematical mindsets.

Saul’s comment highlights how interventions focused on students’ mathematical mindsets are not likely to have substantive change in education because they do not disrupt the oppressive conditions of the *system* of schooling and learning and put the onus of change on students from historically marginalized (yet resilient) groups (Gutiérrez et al., 2024). That is not to say that such interventions are not worth-while, but that they, alone, cannot significantly shift the educational landscape for historically marginalized (yet resilient) students because their focus is on “tweaking” a system that has continued to harm historically marginalized (yet resilient), rather than working to dismantle it and rebuild anew (Gutiérrez, 2017). As we have seen from Syd and Saul’s reflections, if we do not provide students with opportunities to explore how mathematics can be used in the real world and shift the very structures of our teaching to reflect liberatory pedagogies and models, students are likely to retain the belief that mathematics is algorithmic, abstract, and separate from their world.

In addition to modeling and working to shift teachers’ (and students’) beliefs about the nature of mathematics, Syd’s reflection highlights that it is also important for educators to realize that shifting our courses to reflect disability justice and abolitionist, anti-racist, and queer pedagogies may initially lead to resistance that is grounded in culture shock. In an education system that has reinforced colonial, White supremacist, ableist, and cisheteronormative values from its founding to present day (see Hehir, 2002; Keenan, 2017; Keisch and Scott, 2015) Such a reaction might be experienced by not only White students, but also Black and Brown students, and other students from historically marginalized (yet resilient) groups. Similar reactions of resistance have been found in other studies as well (e.g., Brantlinger, 2014; Gutiérrez, 2013). As educators we must think deeply about how to aid students in navigating their resistance and culture shock. In Syd’s case, space was provided to allow them to wrestle with her discomfort in class debriefs, as well as in conversations with B and the Mathematics Education department chair, and even the invitation to co-author this article. As we can see from Syd’s reflection, such opportunities to openly wrestle with these ideas helped her to unearth the areas she was feeling discomfort, in order to move through that discomfort. Other elements that were essential in supporting Syd and their peers with their discomfort were the explore the elements of brave (Arao and Clemens, 2013) and accountable spaces (Ahenkorah, 2020) and co-create brave/accountable agreements at the start of the semester, and B being open about their own mistakes, insecurities, and discomfort in engaging in this type of liberatory teaching. This mirrors the findings of Diallo and Fribor (2021), who noted similar elements as essential to helping students work through discomfort when experiencing similar liberatory pedagogies.

Saul and Syd's comments also mirror an argument made by Gutiérrez (2013), who wrote, "[w]hen we operate with mathematics as an objective arbiter of truth, we maintain its status as pure, separate from and even superior to other fields. However, similar to [W]hiteness, mathematics holds unearned privilege in society" (p. 10). We see through the comments of Syd and Saul discussed previously, that they had maintained this idea of mathematics as being "pure, separate from and even superior to other fields." Syd's comment about believing the assessment was "less rigorous" because it "lacked numbers," (at least in the traditional sense) feels especially connected to this idea, as does their comment that "for mathematics learning to be effective, not only does it have to be rigorous, which in itself is an implicative idea, but also that it has to be painful." Syd's statement here further supports Gutiérrez's (2013) comments about mathematics operating as Whiteness in society, because, Syd is recognizing that she has internalized these specific ideas of pain and rigor as natural orders of the world, but also notes that ideas of "rigor" are themselves "implicative." Syd's statement here illustrates how the use of liberatory pedagogies in the MPP course have worked to have her (re)consider the implications of their definition of rigor and her notion that mathematics, when tapping into human emotion, must tap into the negative (i.e., "pain") This illustrates why Gutiérrez's has stated that such acceptance of "enduring truths" in mathematics is one way "mathematics becomes a means to control," similar to the way Whiteness is used as a means of societal control.

Thus far, our discussion in this section has highlighted some of the ways that B was able to meet two of the three student learning goals (SLGs) for the course, namely, SLGs 2 and 3 (Waid, 2023a, p. 19):

SLG 2: Students will use mathematical argumentation to construct relevant arguments pertaining to two social contexts, to be determined according to student interests.

SLG 3: Students will learn, through modeling, the basic principles of [and] practical ways to engage in an anti-racist, abolitionist, queer, and disability justice oriented pedagogy.

Saul and Syd's reflections heavily discuss how the use of the social contexts as sites for mathematical argumentation (SLG 2), heavily influenced their developing understandings of how to "engage in engage in an anti-racist, abolitionist, queer, and disability justice oriented pedagogy" (SLG 3) (Waid, 2023a, p. 19). While their discussions of the MPP course shows how their ideas of *mathematics* and the teaching and learning of *mathematics* evolved throughout the course, it was not apparent how their ideas of *proof and proving* evolved, if at all. Upon revisiting this question with Syd and Saul, they indicated that when they were learning mathematics, proof was always something that was to be dreaded and was very formulaic. They noted that the idea of proof did not come up as much in their reflections because the way we engaged in argumentation in class did not feel like proving, since the focus was more on argumentation than "listing things out step by step." When B followed up by asking Saul and Syd specifically about the problem sets, they noted that those opportunities did feel more like their traditional ideas of what proof and proving was, except that they were structured as more open questions (e.g., "is this true? If so, prove it. If not, explain why not"), rather than the more closed proving statements that they were used to encountering (e.g., "prove this statement is true"). They noted that this simple change in phrase helped them to think more deeply about the concepts and justify how they had stumbled upon their conclusions. These reflections indicate that, to some degree, B was able to meet SLG 1, "Students will engage in mathematical problem solving on three problem sets, tackling formal mathematical proofs pertaining to number theory and abstract algebra." To some degree, however, B having to follow up about the connection to proof and proving indicates that Saul and Syd were

still struggling to make sense of the relation between the liberatory pedagogies (queer, anti-racist, and abolitionist) and models (disability justice), within the specific context of mathematical proof and proving, rather than mathematics at large. This has led B to believe that should they teach this course again in the future, there should be a fourth unit added to the overall curriculum of the course, where students are given opportunities to relate the liberatory pedagogies and models not only to mathematics education as a whole, but specifically to the context of proof and proving.

While there is clearly room for improvement, should B have the opportunity to teach the MPP course again, we have all found this experience to be transformative in shifting our mindsets and developing our ideas of what liberatory mathematics teaching and learning might look like in practice. In terms of the MPP course design, the elements that we saw were most powerful to the shifting of mindsets of Saul and Syd (and even B) were as follows:

- The inclusion of a flipped model of instruction, which allowed pre-service teachers to grapple with new information and make sense of their problem sets independently, tailored with supportive and scaffolded opportunities to collaboratively make sense of these problems with their peers and to receive in depth peer feedback on their solution methods.
- The inclusion of *local* issues of social justice as a site for creating mathematical arguments, which enable pre-service teachers to engage in mathematical argumentation while reenvisioning what it means to teach mathematics.
- The tailoring of the course's major content units to students interests (as was done through the student survey at the beginning of the year), which allowed students to engage with social issues that were of interest to them.
- The infusing of and explicit discussions about liberatory pedagogical theories throughout the course, which allowed pre-service teachers to “peek behind the curtain” and understand *why* learning experiences were designed in specific ways and how those experiences connect to specific liberatory pedagogical theories. This exposed pre-service teachers to the theories and practical strategies for implementing them in a more concrete way than is accomplished through simple discussions of theory.

References

- Ahenkorah, E. (2020, September 21). Safe and brave spaces don't work (and what you can do instead). *Medium*. <https://medium.com/@elise.k.ahen/safe-and-brave-spaces-dont-work-and-what-you-can-do-instead-f265aa339aff>.
- Antrop-González, R., & De Jesús, A. (2006). Toward a theory of critical care in urban small school reform: Examining structures and pedagogies of caring in two Latino community-based schools. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 19(4), 409–433.
- Arao, B., & Clemens, K. (2023). From safe spaces to brave spaces: A new way to frame dialogue around diversity and social justice. In *The art of effective facilitation* (pp. 135–150). Routledge.
- Brantlinger, A. (2014). Critical mathematics discourse in a high school classroom: Examining patterns of student engagement and resistance. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 85, 201–220.

- Broekkamp, H., & van Hout-Wolters, B. (2007). The gap between educational research and practice: A literature review, symposium, and questionnaire. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 13(3), 203–220.
- Bernard, T. S. (2021, October 11). Seeding accounts for kindergartners and hoping to grow college graduates. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/10/11/your-money/529-savings-plans-baby-bonds.html>.
- Bhutta, N., Chang, A. C., Dettlin, L.J., & Hsu, J.W (2020, September 28). *Disparities in wealth by race and ethnicity in the 2019 survey of consumer finances*. Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System. <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/notes/feds-notes/disparities-in-wealth-by-race-and-ethnicity-in-the-2019-survey-of-consumer-finances-20200928.html>
- Blakemore, E. (2018, February 6). *How the Black Panthers' breakfast program both inspired and threatened the government*. History.com. <https://www.history.com/news/free-school-breakfast-black-panther-party>.
- Boaler, J. (2016). *Mathematical mindsets: Unleashing students' potential through creative math, inspiring messages and innovative teaching*. Jossey-Bass & Pfeiffer Imprints.
- CAST. (2018). Universal design for learning guidelines version 2.2. <http://udlguidelines.cast.org>
- CBS New York. (2022, June 13). "Food deserts" continue to be a problem in New York City [Video] <https://youtu.be/dKDYDKblcEI>
- Chicago Public Schools Bureau of Student Assessment. (n.d.). *Math problem solving rubric samples handout* [PDF file]. https://web.njit.edu/~ronkowitz/presentations/rubrics/samples/math_probsolv_chicago.pdf.
- City of New York. (n.d.). *Food retail expansion to support health (FRESH)*. NYC.gov. <https://www.nyc.gov/site/planning/plans/fresh2/fresh2-overview.page>
- Coates T. N. (2014, June) The case for reparations. *The Atlantic*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/2014/06/the-case-for-reparations/361631/>
- Diallo, O. K., & Friberg, N. M. (2021). Subverting the white cis gaze: Towards a pedagogy of discomfort, accountability and care in the anthropology classroom. *Teaching Anthropology*, 10(4), 17–35.
- Dubbs, C. (2016). A queer turn in mathematics education research: Centering the experience of marginalized queer students. In M. B. Woods, E. E. Turner, M. Civil & J. A. Eli (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education* (pp. 1041–1048). The University of Arizona.
- Dweck, C. S. (2008). *Mindsets and math/science achievement*. Carnegie Corporation of New York-Institute for Advanced Study Commission on Mathematics and Science Education. http://www.growthmindsetmaths.com/uploads/2/3/7/7/23776169/mindset_and_math_science_achievement_-_nov_2013.pdf
- Enlow, M. [@CmonMattTHINK]. (2021, January 24). *This morning's math with M: Seeing which positive integers we could get by adding &/or subtracting only 5s and 8s. We were able to get each of 1 through 10, at which point M declared that it was possible for all positive integers. I asked for a proof, and she*

gave me one. #tmyk. [Tweet]. Twitter.
<https://twitter.com/CmonMattTHINK/status/1353412050303791104?s=20>

- Ernest, P. (1989). The impact of beliefs on the teaching of mathematics. In P. Ernest (Ed.), *Mathematics teaching: The state of the art* (pp. 249–254). Falmer Press.
- Fasching-Varner, K. J., & Seriki, V. D. (2012). Moving beyond seeing with our eyes wide shut: A response to “There is no culturally responsive teaching here.” *Democracy & Education*, 20(1), 1–6.
- Fletcher, N. & Waid, B. (2024). Communities of care for equity, justice, and culturally responsive practice in math education. *Journal of Humanistic Mathematics*, 14(2), 369–422.
- Flores, M. A. (2016). Teacher education curriculum. In J. Loughran and M. L. Hamilton (Eds.), *International handbook of teacher education*. Springer Press.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum.
- González, R. A. (2024). “I’ve always had the abolitionist spirit in me”: Preservice Teachers of Color and Pedagogies of Abolitionist Praxis. *English Education*, 56(3), 143–169.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2009). Framing equity: Helping students “play the game” and “change the game”. *Teaching for excellence and equity in mathematics*, 1(1), 4–7.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2013). Why (urban) mathematics teachers need political knowledge. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*, 6(2).
- Gutiérrez, R. (2017). Political conocimiento for teaching mathematics. In S. E. Kastberg, A. M. Tyminski, A. E. Lischka, & W. B. Sanchez (Eds.), *Building support for scholarly practices in mathematics methods* (pp. 11–37). Information Age Publishing.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2018). Why we need to rehumanize mathematics. In I. Goffney & R. Gutiérrez (Eds.), *Annual perspectives in mathematics education: Rehumanizing mathematics for Black, Indigenous, and Latinx students* (pp. 1–10). National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Gutiérrez, R., Kokka, K., & Myers, M. (2024). Political conocimiento in teaching mathematics: Mathematics teacher candidates enacting their ethical identities. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 27, 755–781.
- Gutierrez, R. J. (2013). Building "consciousness and legacies": Integrating community, critical, and classical knowledge bases in a precalculus class [Doctoral dissertation]. The University of Arizona.
- Gutstein, E. R. (2016). “Our issues, our people—Math as our weapon”: Critical mathematics in a Chicago neighborhood high school. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 47(5), 454–504.
- Hehir, T. (2002). Eliminating ableism in education. *Harvard Educational Review*, 72(1), 1–33.
- Hersh, R. (1993). Proving is convincing and explaining. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 24(4), 389–399.
- Hodgson, T., & Riley, K. J. (2001). Real-world problems as contexts for proof. *The Mathematics Teacher*, 94(9), 724–728.
- hooks, b. (1997). Homeplace: A site of resistance. In L. McDowell (Ed.), *Undoing place? A geographical reader* (pp. 33–38). Routledge.

- Human Rights Campaign. (2022). *The wage gap among LGBTQ+ workers in the United States*. <https://www.hrc.org/resources/the-wage-gap-among-lgbtq-workers-in-the-united-states>.
- Jackson, R. Stewart-Taylor, F., & Wieland, C. (2020, March 31). Disability justice and mutual aid pedagogy or: How I learned to keep working and teach later on. *The Activist History Review*. <https://activisthistory.com/2020/03/31/disability-justice-and-mutual-aid-pedagogy-or-how-i-learned-to-keep-worrying-and-teach-later-on/>.
- Kafai, S. (2021). *Crip kinship: The disability justice and art activism of Sins Invalid*. Arsenal Pulp Press.
- Kafer, A. (2013). *Feminist, queer, crip*. Indiana University Press.
- Katz, B. P., Thoren, E., & Hernandez, V. (2023). Why should that convince me?: Teaching Toulmin analysis across the curriculum. *PRIMUS*, 33(3), 285–313.
- Keenan, H. B. (2017). Unscripting curriculum: Toward a critical trans pedagogy. *Harvard Educational Review*, 87(4), 538–556.
- Keisch, D. M., & Scott, T. (2015). US education reform and the maintenance of White supremacy through structural violence. *Landscapes of Violence*, 3(3), Article 6.
- Kennedy, M. M. (1997). The connection between research and practice. *Educational Researcher*, 26(7), 4–12.
- Kentucky Department of Education (1992). *211 Kentucky holistic scoring rubric for grade 12 math*. https://web.njit.edu/~ronkowitz/presentations/rubrics/samples/math_probsolv_chi_cago.pdf
- Kotler, P. (n.d.). 12 tools to reduce income and wealth inequality. *The Wicked 7*. <https://www.wicked7.org/12-tools-to-reduce-income-and-wealth-inequality/>
- Lane, S. (1993) The conceptual framework for the development of A mathematics performance assessment instrument. *Educational Measurement: Issues And Practice*, 12(2), 16–23.
- Leyva, L. A. (2022, November). Undergraduate Latin* queer students' intersectionality of mathematics experiences: A borderlands perspective. In A. E. Lischka, E. B. Dyer, R. S. Jones, J. N. Lovett, J. Strayer, & S. Drown (Eds.), *Proceedings of the forty-fourth annual meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the psychology of mathematics Education*. Middle Tennessee State University.
- Love, B. L. (2019). *We want to do more than survive: Abolitionist teaching and the pursuit of educational freedom*. Beacon Press.
- Love, B. L. (2021). The 2020 Charles H. Thompson lecture-colloquium presentation: We cannot just research racism: Abolitionist teaching & educational justice. *Journal of Negro Education*, 90(2), 153–157.
- Mendick, H. (2006). *Masculinities in mathematics*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Miller, R. A. (2020). Out of (queer/disabled) time: Temporal experiences of disability and LGBTQ+ identities in US higher education. *Critical Education*, 11(16), 1–20.
- Mitchell, D., Snyder, S., & Ware, L. (2014). "[Every] child left behind" curricular cripistemologies and the crip/queer art of failure. *Journal of Literary & Cultural Disability Studies*, 8(3), 295–314.

- National Association of Black Journalists (2020, June). NABJ statement on capitalizing Black and other racial identities. <https://nabjonline.org/news-media-center/styleguide/>
- New York State (n.d.). *Food Safety Inspections - Current Ratings*. Data.NY.Gov [SAS Data file]. Retrieved from <https://data.ny.gov/Economic-Development/Food-Safety-Inspections-Current-Ratings/d6dy-3h7r/data>
- Nolan, K. (2014). Discursive productions of teaching and learning through inquiry: Novice teachers reflect on becoming a teacher and secondary mathematics. In L. Thomas (Ed.), *Becoming teacher: Sites for teacher development in Canadian teacher education* (pp. 258–288). CATE.
- Nolan, K. (2022, February). The role of pedagogical modeling in being/becoming a culturally responsive mathematics teacher educator. In *Twelfth Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (No. 15).
- Olawale, B. E., Mncube, V. S., & Harber, C. (2021). Critical Social Pedagogy in Mathematics Teacher Education. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(6), 93–104.
- Pólya, G. (1945). *How to solve it: A system of thinking which can help you solve any problem*. Princeton University Press.
- Poole, J. M., & Zerafa, S. (2023). No more deadlines? Tracing transcerceral time in ‘critical’ social work education. *Critical and Radical Social Work*, 11(3), 347–359.
- Raymond, A. M. (1997). Inconsistency between a beginning elementary school teacher's mathematics beliefs and teaching practice. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 28(5), 55–576.
- Sanchez, S. (2023). Review of the book *We want to do more than survive: Abolitionist teaching and the pursuit of educational freedom*, by B. Love. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 36(4), 511–516.
- Sins Invalid (2020, June 16). *What is disability justice?* <https://www.sinsinvalid.org/news-1/2020/6/16/what-is-disability-justice>
- Spaulding, E. C., Adams, J., Dunn, D. C., & Love, B. L. (2021). Freedom dreaming antiracist pedagogy dreams. *Language Arts*, 99(1), 8–18.
- TED-Ed. (2022, October 11). *Is inequality inevitable* [Video]. YouTube. https://youtu.be/rEnf_CFoyv0.
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B18140: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by disability status by sex for the civilian noninstitutionalized population 16 years and over with earnings* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce. Retrieved from <https://data.census.gov/table?q=disability+in+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B18140>.
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017>.
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017A: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (White alone)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017A>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017B: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (Black or African American Alone)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017B>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017C: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (American Indian and Alaska Native Alone)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017C>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017D: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (Asian alone)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017D>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017E: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (Native Hawaiian and other Pacific Islander alone)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT5Y2021.B20017E>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017F: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (Some other race)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017F>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017G: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (Two or more races)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017G>.

U.S. Census Bureau. (2021). B200017H: *Median earnings in the past 12 months (in 2021 inflation-adjusted dollars) by sex by work experience in the past 12 months for the population 16 years and over with earnings in the past 12 months (White alone, not Hispanic or Latino)* [SAS Data file]. U.S. Department of Commerce.

<https://data.census.gov/table?q=earnings+in+the+past+12+months+New+York+city&tid=ACSDT1Y2021.B20017H>.

Vermont Department Of Education (N.D.) 207 Vermont math problem solving criteria. https://Web.Njit.Edu/~Ronkowitz/Presentations/Rubrics/Samples/Math_probsolv_chicago.Pdf

- Waid, B. E. (2018). *Pre-service mathematics teacher beliefs and growth mindset assessment practices* [Doctoral dissertation]. Columbia University.
- Waid, B. (2020). Supporting LGBTQ+ students in K–12 mathematics. *Mathematics Teacher: Learning and Teaching PK-12*, 113(11), 874–884.
- Waid, B. (2023a) *Mathematical Proof and Proving* [Syllabus]. New York University.
- Waid, B (2023b). Liberatory, antiracist mathematics education for Black queer and trans youth. In M. Strutchens, G. Krause, D. Y. White, & J. Bay-Williams (Eds.), *Antiracist mathematics education* (pp. 237–249). TODOS: Mathematics for ALL.
- Waid, B (2023c) What does 2SLGBTQIA+ identity and other non-normative identities have to do with mathematics teaching and learning? *Teaching for Excellence and Equity in Mathematics*, 14(1), 38–41.
- Waid, B. (2023d). *Mathography Part 2 Assignment Handout*. New York University.
- Yoshinobu, S. T. (2003). Mathematics, Politics, and Greenhouse Gas Intensity: An Example of Using Pólya's Problem-Solving Strategy. *The Mathematics Teacher*, 96(9), 646–648.